

THE EFFECT OF GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES TOWARDS CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION AND WILLINGNESS TO PAY PREMIUM: MEDIATION AND MODERATION ANALYSIS

Hadith Fadhillah¹, Wahyuningsih Santosa^{2*}, Dorina Widowati³, Ratna Darasih⁴
^{1,2,3,4}Universitas Trisakti

Received : 15 January 2026
Revised : 31 January 2026

Accepted : 20 February 2026
Published : 28 February 2026

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of green supply chain management practices on consumers' purchase intention and willingness to pay premium using mediation and moderation analysis. This study obtained data by distributing online questionnaires to Generation Z and Millennial consumers who had purchased products from coffee shops that had implemented green supply chain management practices in Jakarta. The sample used in this study consisted of 289 respondents. The data analysis method used was SEM-PLS analysis using SmartPLS software. The results of this study indicate that green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on perceived product performance, willingness to pay premium, and consumer purchase intention. The results also show that perceived product performance mediates purchase intention but does not mediate consumers' willingness to pay more. Consumers' moral orientation towards the environment does not moderate the direct effect of green supply chain management practices on the other three variables.

Keywords: *Consumer Moral Orientation towards the Environment; Consumer Perceived Product Performance; Consumer Purchase Intention; Consumer Willingness to Pay More; and Green Supply Chain Management Practices.*

INTRODUCTION

Over the past two decades, the world has faced a variety of complex environmental and social issues (wicked problems), such as climate change, increasing waste, and disruptions to global supply chains. These challenges demand changes in business practices, shifting from profit-oriented to sustainability. Elkington's Triple Bottom Line concept emphasizes that a company's success is measured not only by profit but also by people and planet. Therefore, companies are required to integrate economic, social, and environmental interests into their operations. In a management context, this is closely related to the concept of operations management, which is the activity of managing resources to produce valuable goods or services (Heizer et al., 2024). One crucial aspect of operations management is supply chain management, which is the process of coordinating all activities from raw materials to products to consumers to increase customer value. An effective supply chain focuses not only on cost efficiency but also on sustainable value creation.

With the growing environmental awareness, the concept of Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM) has emerged. GSCM is the integration of environmental aspects into all supply chain activities, from raw material procurement and production, distribution, and waste management. This practice encompasses various activities such as reduce, reuse, recycle, and reverse logistics, aimed at minimizing negative environmental impacts while improving company performance (Herrmann et al., 2021; Majeed et al., 2025). The implementation of green supply chain management practices not only impacts operational efficiency but also influences consumer perceptions of products. According to consumer behavior theory, consumers evaluate a product through a stimulus process that includes exposure, attention, and interpretation (Solomon & Russell, 2024). In this process, consumers form perceptions of the product's perceived quality or performance, which then influence purchasing decisions. Furthermore, value perception theory explains that consumers compare the benefits obtained with the costs incurred. If consumers perceive an environmentally friendly product to have higher value, they tend to have greater purchase intention and are even willing to pay a premium price (willingness to pay more). This is in line with previous research showing that environmentally friendly practices can improve consumer value perceptions and purchasing decisions. However, in practice, there is an attitude-

THE EFFECT OF GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES TOWARDS CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION AND WILLINGNESS TO PAY PREMIUM: MEDIATION AND MODERATION ANALYSIS

Hadith Fadhillah et al

behavior gap, a gap between consumer attitudes and behavior. Although many consumers express concern for the environment, not all of them realize this in their purchasing decisions. This phenomenon indicates that other factors, such as perceived product quality and price, remain primary considerations in consumer behavior. In addition to perception, consumers' moral orientation toward the environment is also an important aspect in explaining consumer behavior. Based on consumer identity and moral orientation theory, consumers tend to choose products that align with their values and self-identity (Solomon & Russell, 2024). Consumers with a strong environmental moral orientation are more likely to support environmentally friendly products and avoid products that damage the environment. However, the influence of this moral orientation is not always consistent because it can be influenced by situational factors such as price and product availability.

In an industrial context, the food and beverage sector, particularly coffee shops, is a relevant industry to study. This industry produces large amounts of waste and consumes significant resources in its operational processes. In Indonesia, the increase in coffee consumption and the number of coffee shops demonstrates high market potential, but also increases pressure on the environment. On the other hand, although consumer awareness of environmentally friendly products is increasing, there is a gap between consumer intentions and actual behavior. Many consumers want to purchase sustainable products, but only a small percentage actually do so. This indicates that the implementation of green supply chain management practices has not been fully understood and translated into perceived benefits by consumers. A lack of understanding of the influence of green supply chain management practices on consumer purchase intention and willingness to pay more can impact the ineffectiveness of corporate strategies. Therefore, research is needed that examines this relationship more deeply, taking into account the mediating role of perceived product performance and the moderating role of consumers' moral orientation toward the environment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Green Supply Chain Management

Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM) is a concept that integrates environmental aspects into all supply chain activities, from raw material procurement and production processes, distribution, and waste management. GSCM aims to minimize negative environmental impacts without compromising a company's operational and economic performance. According to Herrmann et al. (2021), GSCM practices encompass three main dimensions: strategy, innovation, and operations. These practices include green procurement, eco-design, environmentally friendly production, and reverse logistics. The implementation of GSCM can increase resource efficiency, reduce waste, and enhance a company's image in the eyes of consumers.

Consumer Perceived Product Performance

Consumer-perceived product performance is a subjective evaluation of the quality and benefits of the product received. This perception is formed through a stimulus process consisting of exposure, attention, and interpretation (Solomon & Russell, 2024). Consumers evaluate products based on their experience, information, and expectations. The higher the perception of product performance, the greater the likelihood of consumer satisfaction and the greater the likelihood of making a purchase. Therefore, this perception is a crucial factor in influencing consumer behavior.

Consumer Purchase Interest

Consumer purchase intention is an individual's tendency or intention to purchase a product based on previous evaluations. Purchase intention is influenced by various factors such as perceived quality, product value, price, and brand image. In consumer behavior theory, purchase intention is the stage before an actual purchase decision. Consumers who have a positive perception of a product, including environmentally friendly products, tend to have higher purchase intention. Therefore, purchase intention is often used as an early indicator in predicting purchasing behavior.

Consumer Willingness to Pay More

Consumer willingness to pay more is the level of consumer readiness to pay a higher price than the normal price for a product. This typically occurs when consumers perceive a product to have added value, such as better quality or environmental friendliness. This concept is related to the theory of perceived value, where consumers compare the benefits received with the costs incurred. Products with high environmental value are often perceived as having additional benefits, thus increasing consumers' willingness to pay a premium price.

THE EFFECT OF GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES TOWARDS CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION AND WILLINGNESS TO PAY PREMIUM: MEDIATION AND MODERATION ANALYSIS

Hadith Fadhillah et al

Consumer Moral Orientation towards the Environment

Consumer moral orientation toward the environment is the level of concern and ethical values consumers hold toward environmental issues. Consumers with a strong moral orientation tend to choose environmentally friendly products and avoid products that damage the environment. Based on consumer identity theory, individuals use products as a means to express their values and identity. Therefore, a moral orientation toward the environment can influence purchasing decisions and strengthen the relationship between company practices and consumer behavior.

METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach with a survey method and is included in causal research that aims to examine the effect of green supply chain management practices on consumer purchasing intention and willingness to pay more, by considering the mediating role of perceived product performance and the moderating role of consumer moral orientation towards the environment. Data were collected cross-sectionally through the distribution of online questionnaires to Generation Z and Millennial consumers who have purchased products from coffee shops that implement environmentally friendly practices in Jakarta. The sampling technique used purposive sampling with a total of 289 respondents. The research instrument used a Likert scale of 1–5, and the data obtained were analyzed using the Structural Equation Modeling method based on Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) with the help of SmartPLS software, which includes validity and reliability tests, as well as hypothesis testing both directly, mediation, and moderation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis Testing Results

Table 1. Hypothesis Testing Results

	Hypothesis	Original Sample	p-value	Decision
H1.	Green supply chain management practices have a positive impact on perceived product performance . consumer.	0.294	0,000	Supported
H2.	Practice management supply chain green positive influence to consumer willingness to pay more.	0.283	0.002	Supported
H3.	Green supply chain management practices have a positive impact on consumer purchasing interest.	0.229	0.003	Supported
H4.	Consumer perceived product performance has a positive effect on consumer willingness to pay more.	0.209	0.039	Supported
H5.	Consumer perceived product performance has a positive influence on purchasing interest. Consumer	0.327	0,000	Supported
H6.	Green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumers' willingness to pay more, mediated by consumer-perceived product performance.	0.062	0.064	Not Supported
H7.	Green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumer purchasing interest, mediated by product performance perceived by consumers.	0.096	0.003	Supported
H8.	Green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumers' willingness to pay more, moderated by Consumer Moral Orientation towards the Environment.	0.029	0.145	Not Supported

THE EFFECT OF GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES TOWARDS CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION AND WILLINGNESS TO PAY PREMIUM: MEDIATION AND MODERATION ANALYSIS

Hadith Fadhillah et al

	Hypothesis	Original Sample	p-value	Decision
H9.	Green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumer-perceived product performance, moderated by consumer moral orientation towards the environment.	-0.032	0.024	Supported
H10.	Green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumer purchasing intention, moderated by consumer moral orientation towards the environment.	0.023	0.060	Not Supported

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Green Supply Chain Management Practices on Consumer-Perceived Product Performance

The results of testing the first hypothesis demonstrated that green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumer-perceived product performance. This suggests that the better the green supply chain management practices implemented by a company, the greater the perceived product performance of Gen Z and Millennial consumers in companies in the coffee shop industry in Jakarta. These results support previous research that found that consumers perceive better product performance and increased satisfaction when using products from companies that have implemented green supply chain management practices (Gupta et al., 2023; Kim & Lee, 2018). These results also support previous research by Karim et al. (2024) and Lee et al. (2021) that found that consumer-perceived product performance increases when using products from companies that implement green supply chain management practices.

The results of the hypothesis test indicate that coffee shops that implement environmental management systems in their supply chain practices provide greater benefits to consumers who purchase and use the products. Furthermore, coffee shops that source raw materials from suppliers that meet environmental sustainability targets, design products with minimal energy consumption, and utilize equipment as low as possible have greater value for consumers. For example, Kedai Kopi Tuku supplies raw coffee and palm sugar from trained partner farmers, making consumers feel healthier from consuming these products (Silaban, 2025). Consumers perceive the benefits of lower environmental emissions because raw materials are sourced from closer locations using environmentally friendly methods. Thus, green supply chain management practices can improve product performance as perceived by consumers. Although the test results show a significant direct effect, the magnitude of the effect value of 29.4 percent indicates that green supply chain management practices only play a role in almost one-third of the product performance as perceived by consumers. This indicates that approximately 71.6 percent of product performance is determined by other factors outside the research model. This indicates that the role of green supply chain management practices is quite moderate in influencing the benefits and value obtained from the consumer perspective.

The Impact of Green Supply Chain Management Practices on Consumer Willingness to Pay More

The results of testing the second hypothesis demonstrated that green supply chain management practices positively influence consumer willingness to pay more. This suggests that the better a company's green supply chain management practices, the higher Gen Z and Millennial consumers are willing to pay for products from companies in the coffee shop industry in Jakarta. These findings support previous research that found consumers are willing to pay higher prices for products from companies implementing green supply chain management practices (Karim et al., 2024; Loaiza-Ramírez et al., 2022). These findings also support other research that found green supply chain management practices positively influence consumer willingness to pay more (Gupta et al., 2023; Sun & Yoon, 2022).

The results of this hypothesis test indicate that coffee shops with environmental certifications and sourcing from certified suppliers will encourage consumers to pay more because these practices can help preserve the environment. Consumers are also willing to pay higher prices if the coffee shop collaborates with consumers to design more environmentally friendly products and production processes. For example, Starbucks holds general shareholder meetings, public exposes, and publishes sustainability reports regularly at least once a

THE EFFECT OF GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES TOWARDS CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION AND WILLINGNESS TO PAY PREMIUM: MEDIATION AND MODERATION ANALYSIS

Hadith Fadhillah et al

year (MAP, 2024). The results of these meetings communicate to consumers the reasons for the relatively higher product prices in the market. These practices also allow Starbucks to survive in the market despite having products with relatively higher prices compared to similar products (Feirisa, 2023). Therefore, the better the implementation of green supply chain management practices by coffee shops, the higher consumers are willing to pay for the products offered. Although the test results showed a positive effect, the influence value of 28.3 percent indicates that other, more significant factors are considered when consumers purchase products from green supply chain management practices. When faced with a choice, consumers are more willing to pay more for conventional products that are superior in other aspects than for green products. This indicates that products from green supply chain management practices are not competitive enough to compete in the market.

The Influence of Green Supply Chain Management Practices on Consumer Purchase Intention

The results of testing the third hypothesis demonstrated that green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumer purchasing intention. This suggests that the better a company implements green supply chain management practices, the higher Gen Z and Millennial consumers' purchasing intention for products from the coffee shop industry in Jakarta. These findings support previous research that found increased consumer purchasing intention for products from companies with green supply chain management practices (Karim et al., 2024; Loaiza-Ramírez et al., 2022). Other research also suggests that internal and external green supply chain practices can increase consumer satisfaction, leading to greater consumer interest in purchasing green products (Kim & Lee, 2018; Lee et al., 2021).

The results of testing this hypothesis indicate that coffee shops with product designs that can be reused, recycled, or reused will be more attractive to consumers than non-green products. Furthermore, consumers will be more interested in purchasing products from coffee shops if the company selling them has an environmentally friendly management system and regularly supplies raw materials from suppliers who also have environmental conservation targets. For example, Kedai Kopi Nako recycles consumer plastic packaging at its waste management facility (Werdiono, 2025). Recycled packaging increases consumer purchasing interest, making them more willing to purchase green products than non-green ones.

Although the results of the hypothesis testing showed an effect, the magnitude of the effect of green supply chain management practices on consumer purchasing intention was small, at 22.9 percent. This influence has nearly the same consequences as consumer willingness to pay more, meaning consumers only slightly consider green supply chain management practices seriously when making purchases. Conventional products have a better chance of being more popular than products produced using green supply chain management practices.

The Influence of Consumer Perceived Product Performance on Consumer Willingness to Pay More

The results of testing the fourth hypothesis indicate that consumer-perceived product performance has a positive effect on consumer willingness to pay more. This indicates that the better the product performance perceived by consumers, the higher the willingness of Gen Z and Millennial consumers to pay. These results support previous research that states that consumer-perceived product quality has an indirect effect on consumer willingness to pay more through green brand equity (Akturan, 2020; de Medeiros et al., 2016). These results also support the results of other studies that state that product quality and perceptions of product performance influence consumer willingness to pay more (Gomes et al., 2023; Kim & Lee, 2018).

The results of this study indicate that the added benefits of green products make consumers willing to pay more than non-green products. Furthermore, the study also found that consumers remain loyal to products that address multiple environmental issues even when their prices change. Consumers will also continue to purchase products with green brands because the benefits they offer exceed the price they pay. For example, consumers are willing to pay more for coffee made with plant-based milk, such as oat milk. This is because these milks require less land and energy to produce, thus reducing environmental emissions overall (Riofrio & Baykara, 2022). Thus, consumers perceive green products as more beneficial to their health.

Although the test results show that consumer-perceived product performance influences consumer willingness to pay more, the effect size of 20.9 percent indicates that consumers only consider about one-fifth of product performance when making purchases based on this research model. This indicates that consumers are only slightly influenced when asked to compare the benefits of conventional and environmentally friendly products. Consumers are likely to prefer conventional products that offer greater value and performance due to the additional benefits they receive compared to environmentally friendly products.

The Influence of Consumer Perceived Product Performance on Consumer Purchase Interest

The results of the study on the fifth hypothesis indicate that consumer-perceived product performance has a positive effect on consumer purchase intention. This indicates that the better the product performance perceived by consumers, the higher the purchase intention of Gen Z and Millennial consumers for coffee shop companies in Jakarta. These results support previous research that states that consumer-perceived product performance has an influence on consumer purchase intention (Ariffin et al., 2016; Kumar et al., 2025). These results also support previous research that states that consumer-perceived product effectiveness performance has a positive effect on long-term purchase intention (Tan et al., 2025; Waris & Hameed, 2020).

The results of this study indicate that the added value of environmentally friendly products can increase consumer effort in purchasing green products. Furthermore, the benefits and added value gained from green products can increase consumer involvement in purchasing these products in their daily lives. Thus, consumer-perceived product performance or performance in green products can increase consumer purchase intention for green products. For example, Fore Coffee Shop uses packaging that avoids hazardous materials, making consumers feel safe and healthy, thus encouraging them to regularly purchase coffee at the coffee shop (Fore, 2024). Although this hypothesis, valued at 32.7 percent, represents the largest influence in testing the direct effect hypothesis, it still only has a moderate impact on consumer purchase intention. Consumers perceive a third of the value or benefits derived from green products when deciding to purchase them. Products that provide benefits and value in other aspects may potentially be more desirable than products that excel solely through green supply chain management practices.

The Effect of Green Supply Chain Management Practices on Consumer Willingness to Pay More as Mediated by Consumer-Perceived Product Performance

The results of the study on the sixth hypothesis indicate that green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumer willingness to pay more, not mediated by consumer-perceived product performance. This indicates that consumer-perceived product performance does not act as an intermediary or explain the relationship between green supply chain management practices and consumer willingness to pay more. The results of this study contradict the results of studies by Loaiza-Ramírez et al. (2022) and Karim et al. (2024) which state that consumer-perceived product performance has a mediating role in this influence. The results of this study also do not support the studies by González-Viralta et al. (2023) and Leonardo (2023) which state that consumer-perceived product quality in green products has a positive effect on consumer loyalty.

The results of this study indicate that the added value generated by products produced through environmentally certified supply chains is not sufficient to increase consumers' willingness to pay more. Furthermore, consumers do not perceive any added benefit and are willing to pay more when coffee shops use environmentally friendly packaging that can be recycled or reused. The added benefit generated by green products that source raw materials from suppliers that meet environmental sustainability targets does not increase consumers' willingness to pay more for green products. For example, consumers do not perceive any benefit or added value from products using plastic packaging in the majority of coffee shops in Jakarta. Plastic packaging, which can have a negative impact on the environment, is always the preferred choice when serving coffee for dine-in or takeaway. As a result, consumers are more skeptical of coffee shops' commitment to environmentally friendly supply chain management practices and are therefore reluctant to pay more (Kamil, 2023). The results of this study are also reflected in the hypothesized effect size of 6.2 percent. The weakness of the mediation effect can also be compared with the descriptive statistical data for the mean of the consumer willingness to pay more variable, which is approximately four. This indicates that although consumers are positively willing to pay more, this positivity does not contribute to concrete actions. This accurately describes the gap in attitudes toward consumer behavior.

The Influence of Green Supply Chain Management Practices on Consumer Purchase Intention Mediated by Consumer Perceived Product Performance

The results of the study on the seventh hypothesis indicate that green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumer purchase intention, mediated by consumer-perceived product performance. This indicates that consumer-perceived product performance acts as an intermediary or explains the relationship between green supply chain management practices and consumer purchase intention. The better

THE EFFECT OF GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES TOWARDS CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION AND WILLINGNESS TO PAY PREMIUM: MEDIATION AND MODERATION ANALYSIS

Hadith Fadhillah et al

a company's green supply chain management practices, the better consumer-perceived product performance will be, and this will continuously increase consumer purchase intention. These results support the findings of research conducted by Loaiza-Ramírez et al. (2022) and Karim et al. (2024), which stated that consumer-perceived product performance plays a mediating role in this influence. These results also support the results of other previous studies that stated that the perception of green product performance is higher than that of non-green products, thereby increasing consumer trust and increasing consumer purchase intention (Kim & Lee, 2018; Möller & Herm, 2021).

The results of this study indicate that the added value generated by products manufactured with environmentally friendly packaging can increase consumer purchasing interest in green products. Furthermore, the benefits and performance of products that implement environmental management will increase the likelihood of buyers purchasing green products in the future. Companies that implement green supply chain management practices from upstream, such as suppliers, by ensuring that suppliers also practice environmentally friendly practices will increase overall consumer purchasing interest because the performance of a product is perceived to be improved. For example, Fore Coffee uses more biodegradable plastic materials. These materials are obtained from suppliers who can produce more environmentally friendly packaging (Fore, 2024). More environmentally friendly packaging increases the added value perceived by consumers, thus making them interested in purchasing green products.

Although consumer-perceived product performance has been shown to mediate the influence of green supply chain management practices on consumer purchase intention, the influence value of 9.6 percent indicates that the mediating variable is very weak as an intermediary between the two variables. This indicates that green products play a very small role in product performance, so consumers can easily ignore the benefits of environmentally friendly products when deciding to make a purchase. Conventional products that can provide more non-environmental benefits have the potential to be superior in the eyes of consumers compared to products that excel through green supply chain management practices.

The Effect of Green Supply Chain Management Practices on Consumer Willingness to Pay More Moderated by Consumer Moral Orientation towards the Environment

The results of the study on the eighth hypothesis indicate that consumers' moral orientation towards the environment does not moderate the positive influence of green supply chain management practices on consumers' willingness to pay more. This indicates that consumers' moral orientation towards the environment does not play a role in influencing the strength of the influence between green supply chain management practices and consumers' willingness to pay more. The results of this study contradict the results of studies by Loaiza-Ramírez et al. (2022) and Kamboj & Matharu (2021) which stated that consumers' moral orientation towards the environment has a moderating role in this influence. The results of this study also do not support the results of previous studies by Alam et al. (2023) and (González-Rodríguez et al., 2020) which stated that attitudes towards the environment have a positive influence on consumers' willingness to purchase environmentally friendly products.

The results of this study explain the gap between the phenomena that occurred and previous research references. The results of this study found that consumers who believe that green products can reduce pollution do not increase their willingness to pay more if the coffee shop uses environmentally friendly product packaging. Furthermore, consumers who believe that green products can save natural resources do not increase their willingness to pay more when purchasing products from coffee shops with environmental certification. For example, consumers are less confident that products from coffee shops have not fully implemented green supply chain management practices, which creates the phenomenon of greenwashing. This results in consumers being less optimistic about green products being able to save nature and preserve natural resources (Lin et al., 2025). The insignificant results of the hypothesis testing are also reflected in the resulting influence value. The moderating variable showed an influence value of 2.9 percent. However, the mean value in the statistical testing for the moderating variable was approximately four out of five. This indicates that a good understanding of environmental issues does not automatically translate into actual consumer action.

The Effect of Green Supply Chain Management Practices on Consumer-Perceived Product Performance Moderated by Consumer Moral Orientation Towards the Environment

The results of the study on the ninth hypothesis indicate that consumers' moral orientation towards the environment negatively moderates the positive influence of green supply chain management practices on

THE EFFECT OF GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES TOWARDS CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION AND WILLINGNESS TO PAY PREMIUM: MEDIATION AND MODERATION ANALYSIS

Hadith Fadhillah et al

consumer-perceived product performance. This indicates that consumers' moral orientation towards the environment weakens the influence of green supply chain management practices on consumer-perceived product performance. The results of this study are consistent with the results of research by Loaiza-Ramírez et al. (2022) and Li et al. (2022) which stated that consumers' moral orientation towards the environment has a moderating role in this influence. The results of this study also support previous research by Rana & Solaiman (2023) and Ogiemwonyi & Jan (2023) which stated that consumers' moral orientation towards the environment can trigger perceived product performance in environmentally friendly products.

This study found that consumers who understand and care about the environment will weaken their perceptions of the performance of products derived from green supply chain management practices. Consumers who believe that green products can reduce pollution will weaken their perceptions of green products as having higher value. Furthermore, consumers who believe that green products can conserve nature and natural resources do not perceive green products to perform better than those that do not. For example, various coffee shops in Jakarta sell cloth bags as an alternative to plastic bags for taking home large quantities of drinks. Although cloth bags have been proven to reduce carbon emissions, many consumers do not reuse cloth bags when ordering takeout and online motorcycle taxis. This can have a negative impact on the environment because cloth bags generally require more energy to produce and recycle. Factors such as differences in material composition, patterns, and colors in bags can also complicate the recycling process (Fitri, 2023).

A significant hypothesis test result does not preclude the company from evaluating the research findings. A negative value of 3.2 percent indicates that environmentally conscious consumers do not automatically view all implemented green supply chain management practices as having a positive impact on the environment. The differing perspectives held by consumers represent important information that companies need to consider going forward.

The Effect of Green Supply Chain Management Practices on Consumer Purchase Intention Moderated by Consumer Moral Orientation Towards the Environment

The results of the study on the tenth hypothesis indicate that consumers' moral orientation towards the environment does not moderate the positive influence of green supply chain management practices on consumer purchasing intention. This indicates that consumers' moral orientation towards the environment does not play a role in influencing the strength of the influence between green supply chain management practices and consumer purchasing intention. The results of this study contradict the results of studies by Loaiza-Ramírez et al. (2022) and Hoang & Tung (2024) which stated that consumers' moral orientation towards the environment has a moderating role in this influence. The results of this study also do not support the results of other previous studies by Naalchi Kashi (2019) and Sun & Yoon (2022) which stated that there is a significant relationship between environmental concern and attitudes towards purchasing green products.

The results of this hypothesis test explain the gap between the phenomena that occurred and previous research references. The results of this study found that consumers who believe green products can reduce pollution do not necessarily have interest in purchasing products produced using green supply chain management practices. Furthermore, consumers who believe green products can save the environment and conserve natural resources do not strengthen consumer intentions to purchase products from coffee shops that collaborate with consumers in designing environmentally friendly products, production, and packaging. For example, consumers who are increasingly exposed to greenwashing issues will be more skeptical when offered to purchase environmentally friendly products (Lin et al., 2025). Coffee shops that claim to implement green supply chain management practices but do not provide concrete and objective data reduce consumer purchasing interest. The unsupported test results are also reflected in the effect size of 2.3 percent. This indicates that consumers' understanding of the importance of environmental protection is not embedded as a significant value to be realized. This indication is supported by the mean value of the moderating variable, which is approximately four on a scale of five. Consumers who are aware that green products can reduce pollution and conserve natural resources do not realize their attitudes toward appropriate actions.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study indicate that all direct effect hypotheses are supported. Furthermore, the research findings indicate that consumer-perceived product performance mediates consumer purchase intention but does not mediate consumer willingness to pay more. Therefore, it can be concluded that consumers can perceive the value and benefits of green products and are willing to purchase them. However, the value and

THE EFFECT OF GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES TOWARDS CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION AND WILLINGNESS TO PAY PREMIUM: MEDIATION AND MODERATION ANALYSIS

Hadith Fadhillah et al

benefits of green products perceived by consumers are not sufficient to increase consumer willingness to pay more. Finally, the data analysis in this study indicates that all moderation hypotheses are not supported. This indicates that consumers' perception that green products can reduce pollution and maintain environmental sustainability does not reflect this in their daily purchasing behavior. Therefore, the conclusions that can be drawn from this study are:

1. Green supply chain management practices have a positive impact on consumer-perceived product performance.
2. Green supply chain management practices have a positive impact on consumers' willingness to pay more.
3. Green supply chain management practices have a positive impact on consumer purchasing interest.
4. Consumer perceived product performance has a positive effect on consumer willingness to pay more.
5. Consumer-perceived product performance has a positive effect on consumer purchasing interest.
6. Green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumers' willingness to pay more without being mediated by consumer-perceived product performance.
7. Green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumer purchasing interest mediated by consumer-perceived product performance.
8. Green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumers' willingness to pay more, unmoderated by consumers' moral orientation towards the environment.
9. Green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumer-perceived product performance, moderated by consumers' moral orientation towards the environment.
10. Green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumer purchasing intention without being moderated by consumer moral orientation towards the environment.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, W., Jafar, R. M. S., Waheed, A., Sun, H., & Kazmi, S. S. A. S. (2023). Determinants of CSR and green purchase intention: Mediating role of customer green psychology during COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 389. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.135888>
- Akturan, U. (2020). Pay-premium for green brands: evidence from an emerging country. *Journal of Global Responsibility*, 11(3), 219–232. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JGR-03-2019-0034>
- Alam, M. N., Ogiemwonyi, O., Hago, Ibrahim. E., Azizan, N. A., Hashim, F., & Hossain, M. S. (2023). Understanding Consumer Environmental Ethics and the Willingness to Use Green Products. *Sage Open*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440221149727>
- Andriansyah, A. (2023, July 31). BMKG: Fenomena El Nino Bertahan hingga Akhir Tahun 2023. VOA Indonesia. <https://www.voaindonesia.com/a/bmkg-fenomena-el-nino-bertahan-hingga-akhir-tahun-2023/7204967.html>
- Ariffin, S., Yusof, J. M., Putit, L., & Shah, M. I. A. (2016). Factors Influencing Perceived Quality and Repurchase Intention Towards Green Products. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 37, 391–396. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(16\)30142-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(16)30142-3)
- Badan Pusat Statistik. (2025). Statistik Tanaman Perkebunan Tahunan Indonesia. BPS. (2024, May 20). Upah Minimum Provinsi DKI Jakarta (Rupiah), 2024. <https://jakarta.bps.go.id/id/statistics-table/2/MTIzNiMy/upah-minimum-provinsi-dki-jakarta.html>
- BPS. (2025, September 17). Rata-rata Upah/Gaji Bersih Sebulan Pekerja Formal Menurut Kabupaten/Kota dan Lapangan Pekerjaan Utama (rupiah) di Provinsi DKI Jakarta, 2024. <https://jakarta.bps.go.id/id/statistics-table/2/NDUzIzI=/rata-rata-upah-gaji-bersih-sebulan-pekerja-formal-menurut-kabupaten-kota-dan--lapangan-pekerjaan-utama-rupiah--di-provinsi-dki-jakarta.html>
- de Medeiros, J. F., Ribeiro, J. L. D., & Cortimiglia, M. N. (2016). Influence of perceived value on purchasing decisions of green products in Brazil. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 110, 158–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.07.100>
- Dwivedi, A., Nayeem, T., & Murshed, F. (2018). Brand experience and consumers' willingness-to-pay (WTP) a price premium: Mediating role of brand credibility and perceived uniqueness. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 44, 100–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2018.06.009>

THE EFFECT OF GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES TOWARDS CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION AND WILLINGNESS TO PAY PREMIUM: MEDIATION AND MODERATION ANALYSIS

Hadith Fadhillah et al

- Fadhilah, N. N., Zahara, L. M., Januar, I. D., & Tamara, D. (2025). Factors Influencing Gen Z's Green Product Purchase Behavior. *Eduvest - Journal of Universal Studies*, 5(6), 6683–6695. <https://doi.org/10.59188/eduvest.v5i6.51320>
- Fanarioti, V. (2024, November 20). Why “sustainability” has become a buzzword in the coffee industry. *Perfect Daily Grind*. <https://perfectdailygrind.com/2024/11/why-sustainability-is-a-buzzword-in-coffee/>
- Feirisa, D. R. (2023). 10 Alasan Kenapa Harga Starbucks Mahal. *Detikfinance*. <https://finance.detik.com/berita-ekonomi-bisnis/d-6986183/10-alasan-kenapa-harga-starbucks-mahal>
- Firdaus, F. (2023). GREEN PRODUCT PURCHASE DECISION: THE ROLE OF ENVIRONMENTAL CONSCIOUSNESS AND WILLINGNESS TO PAY. *Jurnal Aplikasi Manajemen*, 21(4), 1045–1060. <https://doi.org/10.21776/ub.jam.2023.021.04.14>
- Fitri, S. N. (2023). Tote Bag: Ancaman Baru yang Kurang Disadari. *Kumparan*. <https://kumparan.com/sevillia-nafisa/tote-bag-ancaman-baru-yang-kurang-disadari-1yM2bLgT4lt/2>
- Fore. (2024). Laporan Tahunan dan Keberlanjutan Fore Coffee.
- Gomes, S., Lopes, J. M., & Nogueira, S. (2023). Willingness to pay more for green products: A critical challenge for Gen Z. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 390. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136092>
- González-Rodríguez, M. R., Díaz-Fernández, M. C., & Font, X. (2020). Factors influencing willingness of customers of environmentally friendly hotels to pay a price premium. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 32(1), 60–80. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-02-2019-0147>
- González-Viralta, D., Veas-González, I., Egaña-Bruna, F., Vidal-Silva, C., Delgado-Bello, C., & Pezoa-Fuentes, C. (2023). Positive effects of green practices on the consumers' satisfaction, loyalty, word-of-mouth, and willingness to pay. *Heliyon*, 9(10), e20353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e20353>
- Greenpeace Indonesia. (2025). Kilas Balik Greenpeace 2024. <https://www.greenpeace.org/indonesia/kabar-dan-cerita/kilas-balik-greenpeace-2024/>
- Gupta, V., Sharma, S., & Sinha, S. K. (2023). How sustainable practices influence guests' willingness to pay a price premium in Fiji. *Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes*, 15(3), 269–278. <https://doi.org/10.1108/WHATT-01-2023-0008>
- Hair, J. F. ., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson. Rolph E. (2019). *Multivariate data analysis*. Cengage.
- Heizer, Jay., Render, Barry., & Munson, Chuck. (2024). *Operations management : sustainability and supply chain management (14th ed.)*. Pearson.
- Herrmann, F. F., Barbosa-Povoa, A. P., Butturi, M. A., Marinelli, S., & Sellitto, M. A. (2021). Green Supply Chain Management: Conceptual Framework and Models for Analysis. *Sustainability*, 13(15), 8127. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13158127>
- Hoang, D. Van, & Tung, L. T. (2024). Environmental concern, perceived marketplace influence and green purchase behavior: the moderation role of perceived environmental responsibility. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 44(11/12), 1024–1039. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSSP-03-2024-0111>
- Hoyer, W. D. ., MacInnis, D. J. ., & Pieters, Rik. (2024). *Consumer behavior*. Cengage.
- Inderst, R., Sartzetakis, E. S., & Xepapadeas, A. (2023). Firm Competition and Cooperation with Norm-Based Preferences for Sustainability. *Journal of Industrial Economics*, 71(4), 1038–1071. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joie.12360>
- Jacobs, F. Robert., & Chase, R. B. . (2023). *Operations and supply chain management. The core*. McGraw Hill Education.
- Jakpat. (2024). *Indonesia Consumer on Coffee - 2023 Jakpat Survey Report*.
- Kamboj, S., & Matharu, M. (2021). Modelling the predictors of consumers' willingness to pay premium price for sustainable products. *Journal of Asia Business Studies*, 15(4), 559–583. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JABS-03-2020-0099>
- Kamil, M. H. (2023, December 21). Kedai kopi menjamur, sampah plastik makin menumpuk di Yogyakarta. *Mongabay*. <https://www.mongabay.co.id/2023/12/21/kedai-kopi-menjamur-sampah-plastik-makin-menumpuk-di-yogyakarta/>
- Karim, R. Al, Rabiul, M. K., & Kawser, S. (2024). Linking green supply chain management practices and behavioural intentions: the mediating role of customer satisfaction. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 7(2), 1148–1168. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTI-04-2023-0241>

THE EFFECT OF GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES TOWARDS CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION AND WILLINGNESS TO PAY PREMIUM: MEDIATION AND MODERATION ANALYSIS

Hadith Fadhillah et al

- Kautish, P., & Sharma, R. (2019). Value orientation, green attitude and green behavioral intentions: an empirical investigation among young consumers. In *Young Consumers* (Vol. 20, Issue 4, pp. 338–358). Emerald Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1108/YC-11-2018-0881>
- Kim, H., & Lee, C. W. (2018). The effects of customer perception and participation in sustainable supply chain management: A smartphone industry study. *Sustainability* (Switzerland), 10(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10072271>
- Kotler, Philip., Armstrong, Gary., & Balasubramanian, Sridhar. (2024). *Principles of marketing*. Pearson.
- Kumar, R., Jain, V., Eastman, J. K., & Ambika, A. (2025). The components of perceived quality and their influence on online re-purchase intention. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 42(1), 38–55. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCM-04-2024-6798>
- Lee, C., Lim, S., & Ha, B. (2021). Green supply chain management and its impact on consumer purchase decision as a marketing strategy: Applying the theory of planned behavior. *Sustainability* (Switzerland), 13(19). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su131910971>
- Leonardo, M. C. (2023). The Impact of Green Product Quality on Green Satisfaction Mediated by Green Perceived Value: An Empirical Study of Eco-Friendly Bag Buyers in DKI Jakarta. *International Journal of Social Service and Research*, 3(11), 2954–2964. <https://doi.org/10.46799/ijssr.v3i11.603>
- Li, D., Cheng, G., & Wang, C. (2022). The influence of moral identity on green consumption. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1020333>
- Lia, D. A. Z., Siswanto, E., Wiraguna, R. T., & Wahyudi, H. D. (2025). From Green Marketing to Enhance Green Purchase Intention: The Act of Green Advertisement, Green Brand Loyalty, and Green Brand Innovativeness. *Jurnal Manajemen Dan Kewirausahaan*, 12(2), 163–175. <https://doi.org/10.26905/jmdk.v12i2.13922>
- Lin, W. L., Chong, S. C., Pek, C. K., Yong, J. Y., Ming, K. L. Y., & XeChung, N. L. (2025). The Impact of Greenwashing: Risks and Implications for Corporate Performance and Stakeholder Trust (pp. 77–94). https://doi.org/10.2991/978-2-38476-358-0_8
- Loaiza-Ramírez, J. P., Moreno-Mantilla, C. E., & Reimer, T. (2022). Do consumers care about companies' efforts in greening supply chains? Analyzing the role of protected values and the halo effect in product evaluation. *Cleaner Logistics and Supply Chain*, 3, 100027. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clscn.2021.100027>
- Mahajan, R., Lim, W. M., Sareen, M., Kumar, S., & Panwar, R. (2023). Stakeholder theory. *Journal of Business Research*, 166, 114104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2023.114104>
- Mahama Braimah, S., Amoako, G. K., Abubakari, A., Ampong, G. O. A., & Ofori, K. S. (2023). Green perceived value and consumer attitudes in the light of the SDGs: a replication study from a developing economy. *Society and Business Review*, 18(2), 345–362. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SBR-03-2022-0088>
- Majeed, M., Agarwal, K., & Tijani, A. (2025). *Green Supply Chain Management*. Apple Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003560845>
- MAP. (2024). *Unshakable Passion 2024 Sustainability Report*.
- Möller, J., & Herm, S. (2021). Perceptions of green user entrepreneurs' performance—is sustainability an asset or a liability for innovators? *Sustainability* (Switzerland), 13(6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063580>
- Munaqib, P., Islam, S. B., Darzi, M. A., Bhat, M. A., Al Lawati, E. H., & Khan, S. T. (2025). Antecedents of consumer purchase intention and behavior towards organic food: the moderating role of willingness to pay premium. *British Food Journal*, 127(2), 779–800. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-03-2024-0275>
- Naalchi Kashi, A. (2019). Green purchase intention. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 11(6), 1389–1403. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-06-2019-0120>
- Nazia Haryanti. (2023, June 26). *Indonesia Penyumbang Sampah Makanan Terbanyak Se-ASEAN*. Infid. <https://infid.org/indonesia-penyumbang-sampah-makanan-terbanyak-se-asean/>
- Ogiemwonyi, O., & Jan, M. T. (2023). The correlative influence of consumer ethical beliefs, environmental ethics, and moral obligation on green consumption behavior. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling Advances*, 19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcradv.2023.200171>
- Parsons, Elizabeth., Maclaran, Pauline., Chatzidakis, Andreas., & Ashman, Rachel. (2023). *Contemporary issues in marketing and consumer behaviour*. Routledge.
- Rainer, P. (2023, August 29). *Sensus BPS: Saat Ini Indonesia Didominasi Oleh Gen Z*. <https://data.goodstats.id/statistic/sensus-bps-saat-ini-indonesia-didominasi-oleh-gen-z-n9kqv>

THE EFFECT OF GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES TOWARDS CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION AND WILLINGNESS TO PAY PREMIUM: MEDIATION AND MODERATION ANALYSIS

Hadith Fadhillah et al

- Rana, S. M. S., & Solaiman, M. (2023). Moral identity, consumption values and green purchase behaviour. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 14(10), 2550–2574. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-01-2021-0030>
- Ringle, C. M., Wende, S., & Becker, J.-M. (2024). SmartPLS 4 (4.1.1.4). SmartPLS. <https://www.smartpls.com>
- Riofrio, A., & Baykara, H. (2022). Techno-environmental and life cycle assessment of ‘oat-milk’ production in Ecuador: A cradle-to-retail life cycle assessment. *International Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 57(8), 4879–4886. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijfs.15828>
- Saada, R. (2021). Green Transportation in Green Supply Chain Management. In *Green Supply Chain - Competitiveness and Sustainability*. IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.93113>
- Sahoo, S., & Vijayvargy, L. (2020). Green supply chain management practices and its impact on organizational performance: evidence from Indian manufacturers. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 32(4), 862–886. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMTM-04-2020-0173>
- Sekaran, Uma., & Bougie, Roger. (2020). *Research methods for business : a skill- building approach/ Roger Bougie and Uma Sekaran*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Silaban, M. W. (2025, August 5). Perjalanan Bisnis Keberlanjutan Toko Kopi Tuku, dari Gelas Daur Ulang hingga Agroforestri. *Tempo*. <https://www.tempo.co/ekonomi/perjalanan-bisnis-keberlanjutan-toko-kopi-tuku-dari-gelas-daur-ulang-hingga-agroforestri-2055290>
- Slack, Nigel., Brandon-Jones, Alistair., & Burgess, Nicola. (2022). *Operations management*. Pearson.
- Smartsrapers. (2025). List of Coffee shops in Jakarta. <https://rentechdigital.com/smartscraper/business-report-details/indonesia/list-of-coffee-shops-in-jakarta>
- Sohn, J. W., & Kim, J. K. (2020). Factors that influence purchase intentions in social commerce. *Technology in Society*, 63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2020.101365>
- Solomon, M. R. ., & Russell, C. Antonia. (2024). *Consumer behavior : buying, having, and being*. Pearson.
- Stevenson, W. J. ., & Kull, T. J. . (2024). *Operations and supply chain management*. McGraw Hill.
- Sulaeman, A. (2025, April 13). Sustainability: Milenial Ingin Jadi Konsumen Hijau, tapi Mengapa Sulit Dilakukan? *National Geographic Indonesia*. <https://nationalgeographic.grid.id/read/134232561/sustainability-milenial-ingin-jadi-konsumen-hijau-tapi-mengapa-sulit-dilakukan?page=all>
- Sun, Z. Q., & Yoon, S. J. (2022). What Makes People Pay Premium Price for Eco- Friendly Products? The Effects of Ethical Consumption Consciousness, CSR, and Product Quality. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(23). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142315513>
- Tan, C. N. L., Fauzi, M. A., & Harun, S. A. B. (2025). From perceived green product quality to purchase intention: the roles of price sensitivity and environmental concern. *Marketing Intelligence and Planning*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MIP-10-2024-0703>
- Traoré, O. Z., Tamini, L. D., & Korai, B. (2023). Willingness to pay for credence attributes associated with agri-food products—Evidence from Canada. *Canadian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 71(3–4), 303–327. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cjag.12336>
- Tulder, R. van., & Mil, E. van. (2023). *Principles of sustainable business : frameworks for corporate action on the SDGs*. Routledge.
- Wahyuningsih. (2020). The Attitude of Young People Towards Environmental Issues and Green Products. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Management, Accounting, and Economy (ICMAE 2020)*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/aebmr.k.200915.033>
- Waris, I., & Hameed, I. (2020). An empirical study of purchase intention of energy- efficient home appliances: the influence of knowledge of eco-labels and psychographic variables. *International Journal of Energy Sector Management*, 14(6), 1297–1314. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJESM-11-2019-0012>
- Werdiono, D. (2025, October 27). Kopi Nako Malang Jadi Ruang Bangun Komunitas dan Dekatkan Media. *Kompas*. <https://www.kompas.id/artikel/kopi-nako-malang-ruang-bangun-komunitas-dan-dekatkan-media>
- Widiantari, N., & Rachmawati, I. (2023). Investigating the Factors of Green Purchase Intention on Green Cosmetics in Indonesia. *Journal of World Science*, 2(12), 2082–2098. <https://doi.org/10.58344/jws.v2i12.510>
- Winarni, R. S. D. (2024). The influence of green products on green purchase intention mediated by green brand awareness. *International Journal of Applied Finance and Business Studies*, 12(1), 44–51. <https://doi.org/10.35335/ijafibs.v12i1.285>

THE EFFECT OF GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES TOWARDS CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION AND WILLINGNESS TO PAY PREMIUM: MEDIATION AND MODERATION ANALYSIS

Hadith Fadhillah et al

World Economic Forum. (2024). The Global Risks Report 2024 (19th ed.). World Economic Forum. www.weforum.org.